

Ambai, Ansus, Menawi and Biak Languages in Papua: A Premiere Report of Comparative Study

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Abstract

This study compares the Ambai, Ansus, Menawi, and Biak languages of Saireri Bay, Papua. These non-Austronesian languages are closely related (SIL, 2000). This research tries to identify genetic evidence linking these four languages. 200 fundamental Swadesh words were studied. This research uses a comparative approach including observation, interview, and documentation. Based on lexicostatistics from 200 Swedish basic vocabularies, the highest connected cognates reach 47%, while the lower-level approach 38%. The regency has more linked vocabulary than other languages. Qualitative evidences are common phonological and lexical innovations that reinforce quantitative evidences. PAAMB *j becoming /z/ and /d/, *h becoming /O/ on Biak. Metathesis, omission, and phoneme addition also occurred. After reconstruction, Proto-language Ansus-Ambai-Menawi and Biak (PAAMB) phonemes are five vowels and 15 consonant phonemes. The vowels of PAAMB are I *e, *a, *o, and *u, while the consonants are *p, *m, *h, and *b, *w, *f, *t, *d, *n, *s *r, *j, *k, *g, *y, and *h.

1. Introduction

This research examines the native languages of Saireri Bay, Papua Province, Indonesia. Saireri customary territory is home to tribes in northern Papua Province, mainly coastal regions. The region is surrounded by Biak and Waropen regencies. Numerous studies on Papua's regional/local languages have covered morphology, syntax, and semantics. Language-kinship research are uncommon.

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This research compares languages. It explores the genetic link of non-Austronesian (Papuan) Ambai, Ansum, Menawi, and Biak languages to reconstruct their proto-language using comparative methods (historical comparative linguistic studies). Previous investigations on these languages' grammar indicated parallels in phonology and vocabulary (Capell, 1938; Heeschen, 1982; Dunn et al., 2002; Ross, 2005; De Vries, 2005). This closeness in sound and vocabulary begs the issue of whether these languages are related, blurring the language grouping. Research is required to solve this issue. For the reasons stated above, the researcher is encouraged to participate in a comprehensive research effort on these languages, which has implications for our understandings of linguistic facts, of genetic or ancestral connections of these languages, in order to prove the relationship of these languages based on inherited elements of the language of origin or proto-languages that are thought to have inherited the languages that exist today.

2. Material and Method

Theoretical basis

This study analyzes the genetic link of a collection of languages within language families. It identifies the phonological and morphological similarities of related languages and determines the direction of language expansion (Schmidt, 1992). The notion of genetic categorization (Sidwell, 2002) was used to reconstruct proto-language of Ambai-Ansum-Menawi-Biak languages spoken in Saireri Bay. The proto-form may provide us an overview of the proto-phoneme language's inventory (Ruhlen, 2002; Gonzales, 2019). The comparison of each contemporary language comprises phonology and lexical level to establish grouping based on the proportion of cognate devices, specific patterns in language evolution, and its connection to one another, leading to the conclusion that these languages are closely connected lexicostatistically (Dyen et al., 1992).

Finding a shared ancestor's legitimacy connects and orders languages (Bynon, 1979: 47; Mbakop, 2021). This connotation hypothesis' linguistic form is comparable. Form and meaning similarity is a dependable trait. Words with similar or identical forms and meanings are cognate sets (not loans, coincidences, or universal trends), thought to have the same origin. Systematic and chaotic sound changes in derived languages make up the regularity hypothesis (Cf. Jannah, 2018). A portion of proto language sounds inherited via a derived language's lexicon.

Methodology

This research used the comparative technique (Durie & Ross, 1996) to compare the Ambai, Ansum, Menawi, and Biak languages in Saireri Bay, Papua Province, using 200 Swadesh terms. A common authenticity derived from the same progenitor or mother language is evident in living, regularly used languages. This study was conducted by applying a comparative method to compare the features of the languages diachronically. This method is employed by using Swadesh 200-word list. Qualitative analysis on the search of genetic relationship of languages involves certain techniques to obtain accurate language facts of the common ancestor (proto language) of a related language group by making observation of words (lexicon) statistically, to attempt to establish the grouping based on the percentage of similarities and differences of a language with other languages and also to be able to classify kinship between two or more languages by comparing the vocabulary and the similarities exist. After the 200 basic vocabulary was determined, the lexicostatistics technique then was undertaken. The technique relates to reconstruction approach. The reconstruction approach predicts old-forms of present languages through quantitative examination of genetic relationships.

These ancient forms likely existed before contemporary languages. The approach uses the 200 fundamental Swadesh words to create proto-form etymons for Ambai, Ansus, Menawi, and Biak.

Next, lexical reconstruction was conducted. This work used lexical construction to uncover proto-word sets with comparable meanings in Ambai, Ansus, Menawi, and Biak. The data collected in the field are identified by lexicostatistical method by grouping the basic vocabulary of related languages, choosing identical, similar, and different basic vocabulary, counting which pairs are related words, connecting the results in the form of percentage, and making genealogical lines or a language kinship tree.

3. Results and Discussion

Reconstruction

Lexical Innovation of Sub-Groups A1 A2

PA1	A2	A1	A2	M
*adia	adia	adia	adia	for
*tarai	tarai	tarai	antu	kaku
*bebara	bebara	bebara	bebara	lbyar
*muni	muni	muni	muni	mun
*tarai	tarai	tarai	ruru	ker
*nanina	nanina	nanina	minaifa	dine
*nawana	nawana	newana	nanaifa	diya
*deremu	deremu	deremu	deremu	nakor
*dowiri	dowiri	dowiri	dowai	aku
*airerawa	airerawa	airerawa	ainorerawa	kif ai
*utu	utu	utu	utu	wuk uk
*diri	diru	diru	diru	mandira
*ruti	ruti	ruti	rutawanai	wufe
*ai	ai	ai	ai	ai
*wai	wai	wai	wai	kabrai
*botoru	botoru	botoru	botoru	kyor
*neina	neina	neina	ina	kor

Lexical Innovation of Sub-Groups A1 M

PA	1M	A1	M	A2
*adia	adia	adia	adia	for
*dai	dai	dai	yayai	kamam
*wewasa	wewasa	wewasa	wawa	idok
*beiru	beiru	beiru	bototi	fis
*bebara	bebara	bebara	bebara	ibyar
*derai	derai	derai	worowi	das
*tora	tora	tora	boarua	imbrau
*miraba	miraba	miraba	membabati	mmabrak
*fiabiai	fiabiai	fiabiai	bebamantaw	lba
*muni	muni	muni	muni	mun
*romu	romu	romu	ayah	man

*rika	rika	rika	ria	rik
*nadoni	nadoni	nadoni	natoti	ryoyo
*boa	boa	boa	yawuyoa	wors
*kambaina	kambaina	kambaina	anewraron	ken
*waroi	waroi	waroi	worowi	byingkwan
*boru	boru	boru	kodu	suru
*boa	boa	boa	manua	fyak
*boi	boi	boi	wyorai	muni
*ai	ai	ai	inani	awin
*diang	diang	diang	ayemu	in,ine,ika
*domoya	domoya	domoya	dowatan	dasar
*rerawa	rerawa	rerawa	kerawa	kif
*utu	utu	utu	utu	wuk
*siai	siai	siai	wyeyawa	wese
*ring	ring	ring	boring	rim
*mimoya	mimoya	mimoya	yeriwan	dafbiober
*mei	mei	mei	eyannyui	fnak
*bampi	bampi	bampi	yampi	wan
*diru	diru	diru	diru	mandira
*bunung	bunung	bunung	yanu	wim
*boromu	boromu	boromu	woremu	swadon
*wonomu	wonomu	wonomu	anomu	snon-snon
*dewaroi	dewaroi	dewaroi	tembani	ikwan
*tinang	tinang	tinang	tenam	iknampu
*enemu	enemu	enemu	anemu	snewar
*ai	ai	ai	ai	ai
*rahida	rahida	rahida	raida	meser
*reisa	reisa	reisa		isar
*wai	wai	wai	wai	kabrai
*aibong	aibong	aibong	telur	pnor
*sifo	sifo	sifo	yepo	irauw
*miri	miri	miri	mori	mararif
*nafani	nafani	nafani	wereria	orooba
*botoru	botoru	botoru	botoru	kyor
*kauboi	kauboi	kauboi		arsywek
*tawai	tawai	tawai	pyar	ikak

Lexical innovation of sub group A 2-M

PA	2M	A2	M	A1
Wanan	wanan	wanan	wanan	wam
Adia	adia	adia	adia	for
Waworu	waworu	waworu	waworu	babo
Bebara	bebara	bebara	bebara	ibyar
Muni	muni	muni	muni	mun
Diru	diru	diru	diru	mandira
Ai	ai	ai	ai	ai
Wai	wai	wai	wai	kabrai

*Ambai, Ansus, Menawi and Biak Languages in Papua:
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Botoru botoru botoru botoru kyor

Lexical Innovation of Sub-Groups A1B

PA	1B	A1	B	A2
Ai	ai	ai	ai	ai

Lexical Innovation of Sub-Groups A2B

PA	2B	A2	B	A1
Rwama	rwama	rwama	roma	rwama
Ai	ai	ai	ai	ai

Diagram 1 Family Tree

Language Family of A A1 – A2 – M – B Language Groups Based on Qualitative Evidences

Based on the findings, Ambai, Ansus, and Menawi are related languages. A1, A2, M includes Ambai, Ansus, Menawi, and Biak. The Ambai-Ansus-Menawi subgroup includes Ambai, Ansus, and Menawi.

Diagram 2 Percentage of Similarity

Quantitative Data of Ambai, Ansus, Menawi and Biak Languages

Ambai	-			
Ansus	17	-		
Menawi	47	9	-	
Biak	1	2	0	-
	Ambai	Ansus	Menawi	Biak

According to the graphic, Ansus and Ambai share 17 vocabulary, whereas Menawi and Ambai share 47. One Biak word is in Ambai. 9 vocabulary are shared by Menawi and Ansus. The Biak and

Ansus languages share a vocabulary. There are no connected vocabularies between Biak and Menawi (0), hence no kinship exists.

Diagram 3 Lineage

A1 (Ambai), A2 (Ansus), Menawi, and Biak are related. First, the Ambai, Ansus, Menawi language group is independent from the Biak language group. Second, the subgroups of these three languages (Ambai, Ansus, Menawi) constitute a distinct member. Third, 49% of Ambai, Ansus, and Menawi's native lexicon is subfamily language.

Etimon List

* adia 'fire '

S adia PAIM *adia A1 adia M adia

*ai' mother '

S ai PAIM *ai A1 ai M ai

*ai 'tree

S ai	PA1M *ai	A1 ai	M ai
*aibong 'egg'			
S aibong	PA1M *aibong	A1 aibong	M aibong
*beiru 'few'			
S beiru	PA1M *beiru	A1 beiru	M beiru
*bebara 'swollen'			
S bebara	PA1M *bebara	A1 bebara	M bebara
*Boa 'Self (standing)'			
S boa	PA1M *boa	A1 boa	M boa
*Boru 'two'			
S boru	PA1M *boru	A1 boru	M boru
*Boa 'four'			
S boa	PA1M *boa	A1 boa	M boa
*bampi 'eat'			
S bampi	PA1M *bampi	A1 bampi	M bampi
*bunung 'drink'			
S bunung	PA1M *bunung	A1 bunung	M bunung
*boromu 'mouth'			
S boromu	PA1M *boromu	A1 boromu	M boromu
*botoru 'three'			
S botoru	PA1M *botoru	A1 botoru	M botoru
*dai 'Father'			
S dai	PA1M *dai	A1 dai	M dai
*derai 'swim'			
S derai	PA1M *derai	A1 derai	M derai
*diang 'fish'			
S diang	PA1M *diang	A1 diang	M diang
*domoya 'right'			
S domoya	PA1M *domoya	A1 domoya	M domoya
*diru 'night'			
S diru	PA1M *diru	1A diru	M diru
*dewaroi 'long'			
S dewaroi	PA1M *dewaroi	A1 dewaroi	M dewaroi

*enemu 'stomach'				
S enemu	PA1M*	enemu	A1 enemu	M enemu
*fiabai 'big'				
S fiabai	PA1M*	fiabai	A1 fiabai	M fiabai
*kambaina 'heart'				
S kambaina	PA1M*	kambaina	A1 kambaina	M kambaina
*kauboi 'worm'				
S kauboi	PA1M	*kauboi	A1 kauboi	M kauboi
*miraba 'heavy'				
S miraba	PA1M	*miraba	A1 miraba	M miraba
*muni 'kill'				
S muni	PA1M	*muni	A1 muni	M muni
*mimoya 'straight'				
S mimoya	PA1M*	mimoya	A1 mimoya	M mimoya
*mei 'play'				
S mei	PA1M*	mei	A1 mei	M mei
*miri 'laugh'				
S miri	PA1M*	miri	A1 miri	M miri
*nadoni 'where'				
S nadoni	PA1M*	nadoni	A1 nadoni	M nadoni
*nafani 'not'				
S nafani	PA1M*	nafani	A1 nafani	M nafani
*romu 'bird'				
S romu	PA1M	romu	A1 romu	M romu
*rika 'blood'				
S rika	PA1M	rika	A1 rika	M rika
*rerawa 'skin'				
S rerawa	PA1M	rerawa	A1 rerawa	M rerawa
*rahida 'afternoon'				
S rahida	PA1M	*rahida	A1 rahida	M rahida
*siai 'other'				
S siai	PA1M	*siai	A1 siai	M siai

*reisa 'sharp'				
S reisa	PA1M* reisa	A1 reisa	M reisa	
*sifo 'fly'				
S sifo	PA1M* sifo	A1 sifo	M sifo	
*tora 'walk'				
S tora	PA1M * tora	A1 tora	M tora	
*tinang 'short'				
S tinang	PA1M * tinang	A1 tinang	M tinang	
*tawai 'snaker'				
S tawai	PA1M * tawai	A1 tawai	M tawai	
*utu 'lice'				
S utu	PA1M *utu	A1 utu	M utu	
*wewasa 'wet'				
S wewasa	PA1M *wewasa	A1 wewasa	M wewasa	
*waroi 'jauh'				
S waroi	PA1M waroi	A1 waroi	M waroi	
*wonomu 'name'				
S wonomu	PA1M wonomu	A1 wonomu	M wonomu	
*wai 'rope'				
S wai	PA1M wai	A1 wai	M wai	

The following table shows Ambai, Ansus, Menawi, and Biak's similarity percentages.

Ambai	-			
Ansus	17	-		
Menawi	47	9	-	
Biak	1	2	0	-
	Ambai	Ansus	Menawi	Biak

Based on the chart, Ansus has 17 related Ambai vocabulary and Menawi has 47. Biak has 1 Ambai-related word. Menawi and Ansus share 9 words. Biak and Ansus share vocabulary. Biak and Menawi have no related vocabularies (0), indicating no kinship.

Diagram 3 Lineage

Kinship Lineage of A1 (Ambai), A2, (Ansus), Menawi, Biak Languages

As shown above, A1 (Ambai), A2 (Ansus), Menawi, and Biak are related. First, the Ambai, Ansus, Menawi language group is independent from the Biak language group. Second, the subgroups of these three languages (Ambai, Ansus, Menawi) constitute a distinct member. Third, 49% of Ambai, Ansus, and Menawi's native lexicon is subfamily language.

Etimon List

* adia 'fire'				
S adia	PAIM	*adia	A1 adia	M adia
*ai'mother'				
S ai	PAIM	*ai	A1 ai	M ai
*ai 'tree'				
S ai	PA1M	*ai	A1 ai	M ai
*aibong 'egg'				
S aibong	PA1M	*aibong	A1 aibong	M aibong

*beiru 'few'				
S beiru	PA1M*	beiru	A1 beiru	M beiru
*bebara 'swollen'				
S bebara	PA1M*	bebara	A1 bebara	M bebara
*Boa 'self (standing)'				
S boa	PA1M	*boa	A1 boa	M boa
*Boru 'two'				
S boru	PA1M	*boru	A1 boru	M boru
*Boa 'four'				
S boa	PA1M	*boa	A1 boa	M boa
*bampi 'eat'				
S bampi	PA1M*	bampi	A1 bampi	M bampi
*bunung 'drink'				
S bunung	PA1M*	bunung	A1 bunung	M bunung
*boromu 'mouth'				
S boromu	PA1M*	boromu	A1 boromu	M boromu
*botoru 'three'				
S botoru	PA1M	*botoru	A1 botoru	M botoru
*dai 'father'				
S dai	PA1M	*dai	A1 dai	M dai
*derai 'swim'				
S derai	PA1M	*derai	A1 derai	M derai
*diang 'fish'				
S diang	PA1M	*diang	A1 diang	M diang
*domoya 'right'				
S domoya	PA1M	*domoya	A1 domoya	M domoya
*diru 'night'				
S diru	PA1M	*diru	1A diru	M diru
*dewaroi 'long'				
S dewaroi	PA1M	*dewaroi	A1 dewaroi	M dewaroi
*enemu 'stomach'				
S enemu	PA1M*	enemu	A1 enemu	M enemu

*fiabai 'big' S fiabai	PA1M*fiabai	A1 fiabai	M fiabai
*kambaina 'heart' S kambaina	PA1M*kambaina	A1 kambaina	M kambaina
*kauboi 'worm' S kauboi	PA1M *kauboi	A1 kauboi	M kauboi
*miraba 'weight' S miraba	PA1M*miraba	A1 miraba	M miraba
*muni 'kill' S muni	PA1M *muni	A1 muni	M muni
*mimoya 'straight' S mimoya	PA1M *mimoya	A1 mimoya	M mimoya
*mei 'play' S mei	PA1M*mei	A1 mei	M mei
*miri 'laugh' S miri	PA1M*miri	A1 miri	M miri
*nadoni 'where' S nadoni	PA1M*nadoni	A1 nadoni	M nadoni
nafani 'not' S nafani	PA1M nafani	A1 nafani	M nafani
*romu 'bird' S romu	PA1M romu	A1 romu	M romu
*rika 'blood' S rika	PA1M rika	A1 rika	M rika
*rerawa 'skin' S rerawa	PA1M rerawa	A1 rerawa	M rerawa
*rahida 'afternoon' S rahida	PA1M *rahida	A1 rahida	M rahida
*siai 'other' S siai	PA1M * siai	A1 siai	M siai
reisa 'sharp' S reisa	PA1M reisa	A1 reisa	M reisa

*sifo 'fly'				
S sifo	PA1M* sifo	A1 sifo	M sifo	
*tora 'walk'				
S tora	PA1M * tora	A1 tora	M tora	
*tinang 'short'				
S tinang	PA1M * tinang	A1 tinang	M tinang	
*tawai 'snake'				
S tawai	PA1M * tawai	A1 tawai	M tawai	
*utu 'lice'				
S utu	PA1M *utu	A1 utu	M utu	
*wewasa 'wet'				
S wewasa	PA1M *wewasa	A1 wewasa	M wewasa	
*waroi 'far'				
S waroi	PA1M waroi	A1 waroi	M waroi	
*wonomu 'name'				
S wonomu	PA1M wonomu	A1 wonomu	M wonomu	
*wai 'rope'				
S wai	PA1M wai	A1 wai	M wai	

4. Conclusions

Based on the description above, it is concluded that (1) the kinship of Ambai, Ansus, and Menawi languages is revealed, and their frequency is high, in which the percentage of word relatives (vocabulary) of Ambai and Menawi is 47; Ansus and Ambai have 17 related vocabularies; Menawi and Ansus have 9 related vocabularies; while Menawi and Biak have no related vocabularies (0). The Ambai, Ansus, and Menawi languages are grouped into the same subgroup or family based on quantitative evidence, lexical innovation, and lexicon reconstruction; the Biak language is isolated from the group owing to geographical circumstances. (3) Based on phonemic correspondence, phonetic similarities, and word systems, Ambai, Ansus, Menawi, and Biak in Saireri Bay, Papua Province are classed as non-Austronesian proto languages.

Comparative historical linguistic study on Ambai, Ansus, Menawi, and Biak in Papua Province's Saireri Bay is confined to quantitative and qualitative characteristics, requiring greater research on phonology, morphology, and syntax. The researcher advises that future scholars undertake a similar study utilizing a historical comparative linguistic analysis to verify the relationship of the languages to the surrounding languages, which is helpful for the development of non-Austronesian languages studies.

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